

Impact of Growth of Science and Technology on Fairs and Festivals of Jaipur

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ABSTRACT

The tourism industry is also the fastest growing industry in the service sector. The place of Rajasthan is unique and its contribution very crucial for the Indian tourism industry. The tourism sector tagline of Rajasthan previously called “padharo mahre desh”. has a vast potential in both rural and urban sectors. The tourism sector also employees vast number of people providing livelihood to all. This has transformed Rajasthan in a number of ways. Jaipur in particular has seen a lot of change. Jaipur forms the lifeline of tourism in Rajasthan because of its location, economic resources and its administrative importance.

Key words: Science and Technology, Fairs, Festivals, Jaipur

India is separated from the rest of Asia by the mountains and has a distinct geographical identity. It is a remarkable tourist destination and provides people with diverse experience. The tourism industry generates employment and contributes to social cultural educational and political development and new opportunities in the development story of India. The tourism industry is also the fastest growing industry in the service sector. The place of Rajasthan is unique and its contribution very crucial for the Indian tourism industry. The tourism sector tagline of Rajasthan previously called “padharo mahre desh”. has a vast potential in both rural and urban sectors. The tourism sector also employees vast number of people providing livelihood to all. This has transformed Rajasthan in a number of ways. Jaipur in particular has seen a lot of change. Jaipur forms the lifeline of tourism in Rajasthan because of its location, economic resources and its administrative importance. Science and technology provide an aid to tourism also they help to eliminate the problems faced by the tourism sector. The growth of modern science and technology started with the industrial revolution. The steam engine helped people move faster aiding the tourism industry increasing the participation rate of people in all fairs and festivals . This growth was also aided by invention of aeroplane by wright brothers. After the air transport opened the festivals and fairs become global from local. The temporal growth of science and technology has introduced several changes within the local fairs and festivals of Jaipur in particular. The impact is both positive and negative due to the growth of science and technology and the third industrial revolution. The main festivals and fairs of Jaipur include Gangaur, Teej fair, elephant festival, kite festivals. Due to science and technology festivals like: JLF (Jaipur literature festival) have also come up.

<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/travel/destinations/jaipur-literature-festival-is-back-and-is-bigger-and-better/articleshow/62378896.cms>

<https://www.jaipurmagazine.com/fairs-festivals/gangaur-festival/>

The growth of science and technology had a positive impact in terms of attracting international tourists as most international tourists have come due to the increasing publicity of fairs and festivals on social media. The best package of various companies also attracts international tourists in local fairs and festivals. These festival packages are able to reach the tourists due to increased science and technology and use of social media, television ads, and other sources. The tourists have been on the rise in Rajasthan, in particular, with a significant part of its GDP dependent on the tourism sector. The tertiary sector plays an important role in the economy and society and other sectors in Rajasthan and Jaipur. Increased role of science and technology has transformed lives and livelihoods of the local people of the state.

<https://www.ndtv.com/jaipur-news/the-tale-of-kite-flying-from-the-royal-quarters-of-rajasthan-1648686>

Science and technology also decrease the job difficulties and administrative difficulties of the police department with the help of CCTV monitoring. The police can now monitor all the fairs and festivals with ease. The CCTV cameras around many areas of Jaipur have brought significant changes. This would not have been possible without the use of science and technology. In particular, the CCTV technology is present around significant places like Badi chaupar, Chhoti chaupar, City Palace, etc. These are the places where Gangaur is celebrated in a traditional style and is famous all over the world. Many tourists travel from overseas just to witness the traditional fairs and festivals of Jaipur. This technology of CCTV has decreased the risk of crime around various fairs and festivals of Jaipur. Crimes like chain snatching, theft, etc. can easily be detected using advanced CCTV technology. This has helped in the growth of fairs and festivals in particular. The CCTV technology has also helped in traffic diversion during local festivals of Jaipur. During the Gangaur festival of Jaipur, CCTVs are used for traffic diversion and taking other administrative decisions. This has increased the convenience of citizens as well as the participants of the fairs and festivals. In festivals like the kite festival of Jaipur, other local fairs, the CCTV monitoring can help to detect the winners of various events. In the festival, technology provides help in other necessary functions of the fair and festivals.

<https://www.cityofjaipur.com/jaipur-local/about-jaipur/jaipur-fairs-and-festivals/most-popular-festivals-of-jaipur/>

The growth of science and technology has brought a phenomenon to life the fairs and festivals which were distant from people and confined to places are now a part of their world.

<https://www.travelviewpoint.com/banganga-fair-jaipur/>

This has only been possible due to the televised session and virtual participation of fairs and festivals. Anyone from anywhere can participate in the fairs and festivals through a virtual format. The virtual forms of participation in fairs and festivals include live telecast, e participation, online ticket bookings, online tours and travel apps, online participation through meta verse. This has enabled participation from the participants from personal space. This was the most preferred method during Covid 19. It is also useful in situations where social distancing is necessary and participants cannot come due to inconvenience. The television ensures that the culture of a place is preserved using technology simultaneously this also ensures that the people can participate from their own personal spaces. The growth of television brought down the price of the ticket enabling low and equal policy of ticket pricing in fairs and festivals. High pricing practice for fees is not practised anymore this has ensured accessibility in fairs and festivals and brought people from diverse backgrounds in all festivals. Festivals are not confined to the rich like they used to be earlier. In Gangaur festival During the British era mostly the privileged used to participate slowly this custom has changed slowly. Presently many come to witness the festival irrespective of economic or social status. This has increased diversity in the fairs and festivals of Jaipur. This is an example of positive intervention of science and technology.

<https://newsonair.gov.in/News?title=Festival- of-Gangaur-being-celebrated-across- Rajasthan-with-traditional- reverence-and- gaiety&id=438504>

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